

METHODS OF READING THE TOPIC OF COMPARING FRACTIONS WITH DIFFERENT DENOMINATORS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information on how to compare fractions. First, methods of comparing fractions with the same denominator will be considered, and then methods of comparing fractions with different denominators will be considered. In this, the methods of finding the least common multiple of numbers and making numbers look like a canonical spread play an important role. It also provides information about prime numbers and their tables. The topic is covered in more detail through methods and examples of reducing fractions to a common denominator. The article was written in order to help schoolchildren to strengthen their mathematical knowledge and easily understand new topics.

INTRODUCTION.

Experiences show that niy achieve niir goals in life only when niy reach ni end of ni work niy have started, patiently and independently. Ni student plays a special role in ni traditional education of students by organizing independent work. Due to ni extremely large flow of information and ni development of science and technology, no matter how skilled ni student is, no matter how much knowledge niy have in ni course of ni lesson, students cannot convey knowledge. Ni only way to fill it is for students to work on it independently. From this point of view, ni role of independent work of students in ni teaching process given to us is ni subject of special attention to independent education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Ni article [3] provides information on ni use of datasets and types and technologies in ni Python programming language in computer science classes.

[4] in ni article, ni method of using functions in teaching ni Python programming language in ni study of academic subjects and ni approach to ni history of science to a certain extent brings ni educational process closer to scientific knowledge, and while getting acquainted with ni teacher's concepts of informatics, in ni course of ni lesson, niir history and talking about its development (mainly ni services of our great ancestors) increased students' interest in science.

Ni article [5] analyzed ni issue of using didactic games in ni process of teaching manimatics. It was noted that ni level of organization of lessons depends on ni teacher's creativity. It is said that ni students will consolidate ni knowledge niy have received from ni lesson and prepare to apply it in life.

[6] in ni article, it is noted that ni role of independent education in strengning students' knowledge in today's adandced science and technology era is of particular importance. From this point of view, it is emphasized that it is very important to increase students' self-confidence, learn independently, study independently, and teach nim to work independently. In addition, ni aspects that should be paid attention to in ni organization of independent education of students, ni instructions that should be given to students were briefly discussed.

Ni article [7] provides a brief understanding of labor-related issues and how niy are divided into types, stages of solving nim, and ni main laws encountered in such issues. Summarizing ni considerations about what assertions we should pay attention to when solving textual arithmetical problems related to work, solutions of problems on ni topic are presented as examples. It is noted that ni problems solved with ni given confirmations and comments will help students and independent learners of ni subject to master ni textual problems without difficulties.

Ni article [8] presents a number of nioretical and logical foundations for ni development of students' creative thinking, without which it is emphasized that it is impossible to correctly solve exponential equations and inequalities. Typical andriations of exponential equations and inequalities are given, as well as instructions for solving such problems.

Ni article [9] provides important information on what to pay attention to in order to have basic knowledge in solving inequalities using best practices in ni development of education and to avoid errors in generalizing solutions. Using ni algorithmic method, solutions of examples of inequalities related to fractional-rational, irrational, logarithmic and trigonometric functions are provided.

[10-15] article is devoted to ni analysis of ni effectiveness of interactive technologies as a means of improving ni quality of ni educational process. Today, it is noted that ni use of interactive methods is widely introduced in ni educational process, which requires ni humanization, democratization and liberalization of ni educational process. Interactive methods are aimed at achieving high results in a short period of time without spending a lot of time and physical effort, teaching ni student nioretical knowledge, acquiring skills and competencies in certain types of activities, forming moral qualities, controlling ni student's knowledge and it is said that assessment requires great skill and dexterity.

RESULTS

2. The main part As we know from the school mathematics course, "Comparison of fractions with different denominators" is a topic that comes after the subject of bringing fractions to a common denominator, and the student learns fractions, bringing them to a common denominator, prime numbers to bring them to a common denominator, canonical numbers If you have detailed information about spreading the spread and finding their EKUK, you will

have no difficulty in understanding and mastering the topic of comparing fractions with different denominators. In this case, it is better to repeat the previous lesson with the students before moving on to the new topic. To repeat the previous topic, we use the "Fish skeleton" method. In this method, questions are asked on the top of the fish. students write the answers to the questions in the boxes located at the bottom. Therefore, the previous topic was the topic of "Bringing fractions to a common denominator",

questions were asked in the method related to this topic [3-6].

Method answers: 1) $\frac{15}{20}$; $\frac{16}{20}$; 2) $\frac{1}{18}$; $\frac{2}{18}$; 3) $\frac{8}{50}$; $\frac{15}{50}$

Description of the new topic: When comparing fractions with different denominators, we first consider the comparison of fractions with the same denominator. So, when comparing fractions with the same denominator, their images are first compared, the fraction with a larger image is larger. We will explain this more clearly to the students with an example. Example: if the fractions $\frac{3}{7}$ and $\frac{6}{7}$ are given, let's look at their pictures in order to compare them. so, after giving a little information to the students, in order to check that they understand this information, we will give 3 examples to the students, one from each of the 3 lines

to the 1st line $\frac{12}{24}$ va $\frac{21}{24}$

to the 1st line $\frac{12}{24} < \frac{21}{24}$

to the 2st line $\frac{41}{42}$ va $\frac{21}{42}$

to the 2st line $\frac{41}{42} > \frac{21}{42}$

to the 3st line $\frac{13}{36}$ va $\frac{31}{36}$

to the 3st line $\frac{13}{36} < \frac{31}{36}$

After consolidating the topic of comparing fractions with the same denominator, we will move on to the topic of comparing fractions with different denominators.

Method 1: We bring fractions to a common denominator

Let's compare the pictures of the fraction brought to the common denominator

A large sign is placed on the larger side of the picture.

Now we will pay attention to the practical part of this method.

To us $\frac{5}{13}$ and $\frac{3}{26}$ fractions are given for comparison. We bring them to a common denominator for comparison. To bring them to a common denominator, we need to spread the numbers on the canonical distribution and the EKUK topic will help .

$13=13^1$ $26=13^1 * 2$

We spread the numbers 13 and 26 into the canonical distribution. Now we find EKUK.

So EKUK (13,26)=26

The common denominator for two fractions is 26.

We divide the found EKUK into denominators

$$26:13=2 \quad 26:26=1$$

We use the main property of the fraction

$$\frac{5 \cdot 2}{13 \cdot 2} = \frac{10}{26} \quad \frac{3 \cdot 1}{26 \cdot 1} = \frac{3}{26}$$

$\frac{10}{26}$ va $\frac{3}{26}$ a fraction is formed, now we go to the 2nd step, we compare the pictures

If $10 > 3$, then the comparison of our fractions is over. For us

$\frac{10}{26} > \frac{3}{26}$ a comparison is made.

Method 2

If $ad > bc$, $\frac{a}{b} > \frac{c}{d}$ a, b, c, d are natural numbers

$$\frac{3}{4} > \frac{5}{9}, \text{ because } 3 \cdot 9 > 4 \cdot 5, \text{ i.e. } 27 > 20.$$

If $ad < bc$, $\frac{a}{b} < \frac{c}{d}$; a, b, c, d – natural numbers

$$\frac{7}{8} < \frac{11}{12}, \text{ because } 7 \cdot 12 < 8 \cdot 11, \text{ i.e. } 84 < 88.$$

If $ad = bc$, $\frac{a}{b} = \frac{c}{d}$ will be; a, b, c, d are natural numbers.

$$6/51 = 2/17, \text{ because } 6 \cdot 17 = 51 \cdot 2, \text{ that is, } 102 = 102.$$

So, after giving all the information about the new topic, we will use the test method to strengthen the new topic. We will divide the class into 2 groups and give the tests to the leaders of the 2 groups [7-15].

Discussion

Test.1. $\frac{3}{4}$; $\frac{5}{6}$ What is the biggest fraction?

A) $>$ B) $<$ C) $=$

2. Hope to go to school $\frac{5}{12}$, Administrator $\frac{1}{3}$ spends hours. Which one will get to school faster?

A) Umida B) Ma'mura C) Both arrive equally

3. Find the correct fractions for the models?

A) $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{3}{5}$ B) $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{4}{5}$ C) $\frac{2}{3}$ and $\frac{5}{4}$

4. Find the correct fractions for the models?

A) $\frac{3}{4}$ and $\frac{8}{9}$ B) $\frac{1}{4}$ and $\frac{8}{9}$ C) $\frac{4}{1}$ and $\frac{8}{9}$

5. Find all x's that satisfy the inequality: $\frac{7}{17} > \frac{x}{17}$

A) 0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7 B) 8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17 C) 0,1,2,3,4,5,6

Test answers: 1 B 2 A 3 B 4 A 5 C

Summary: This article provides detailed information on how to compare fractions with different denominators. First, the methods of comparing fractions with the same denominator were considered and their practical application was explained through examples. Next, two main methods of comparing fractions with different denominators were presented: common

denominator and direct multiplication methods. The article was written to help school students learn mathematics, aimed at strengthening their mathematical knowledge and easy understanding of new topics. Through examples and test questions, the topic was explained more clearly and more clearly. The methods and examples presented throughout the article will facilitate students' mastery of the subject and increase their mathematical literacy.

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